

Light Pollution and Astro-tourism: The Case of Melik Plateau

Hatice SARI GÖK¹

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 24 April 2022

Accepted 27 August 2022

Published 30 December 2022

JEL classification:

L83; Z31

Key words:

Light pollution

Tourism

Astro-tourism

Melik Plateau

ABSTRACT

The sky, the stars, the rainbow, and the universe have always piqued people's interest, from ancient times to the present. The night sky can be enjoyed in all its glory in large rural areas that are not harmed by light pollution. For sky observations, places with less light pollution are favored due to heavy light pollution in cities. The concept of astro-tourism was born as a result of this event's transformation into a tourism activity. Astro-tourism is a sort of nature-based tourism that involves traveling to locations where there is no light pollution to observe the sky and celestial occurrences. The Melik Plateau in Isparta Province has been named the darkest place among Turkey's National Parks, with little light and air pollution. As a result, the goal of this study is to determine the current state of astro-tourism activities on the Melik Plateau. For this purpose, a SWOT analysis was made regarding the astro-tourism activities of Melik Plateau.

1. Introduction

The sky, the stars and the universe are areas that people are interested in, curious about and sometimes like to watch. The sky, celestial bodies and the universe, which have always been the subject of curiosity and research from the past to the present, are presented as a natural tourist attraction. Interest in touristic activities presented as space tourism or astro-tourism is increasing day by day. Space tourism is an expensive type of tourism because it necessitates significant financial resources for the implementation process and significant investments for its infrastructure. As a result, only a small number of tourists are able to participate in these activities (Yalçın & Karabacak, 2022: 26). Astro-tourism, on the other hand, stands out as a simple and inexpensive tourism activity that can be carried out using observatory infrastructure in suitable rural locations or portable observing equipment without leaving the world campus. Astro-tourism allows travelers to examine celestial bodies in the company of experienced guides in order to satisfy their inner desires and curiosity (Tadić, 2016).

Light pollution-free surroundings are required for observing the sky. Light pollution in cities is increasing as a result of the increased usage of artificial lights as cities continue to grow in population (Özarabacı, 2017). Light pollution is defined as the usage of light in the wrong direction, at the wrong time, and in the wrong

¹ Assistant Professor, Department of Travel, Tourism and Entertainment Services, Yalvaç Vocational School, Isparta University of Applied Sciences, Isparta, Turkey; haticesarigok@isparta.edu.tr

amount, in a way that disturbs living things. In addition to preventing people from seeing the sky and the elements of the universe, light pollution has severe consequences in a variety of areas, including energy waste, health, the ecosystem, and security (Sogdugan, 2020).

There are two types of reasons for the brightness in the sky at night: natural and artificial. Natural sources of moonlight, starlight, and rays reflected from the sun and other planets are all examples. The source of artificial brightness is the conversion of electrical energies into light energy to create artificial light in the sky. These light filters reflect sunlight directly into the sky, resulting in dazzling backdrops. The stars cannot be seen in the sky because of these backgrounds (Çetegen & Batman, 2005).

Light pollution has a significant impact on amateur and professional astronomers. The photograph of a black night sky in the same place and the image of a night sky with heavy light pollution are practically unrecognizable. It becomes more difficult to discern dim objects as light pollution increases. As a result, professional observatories are built as far away from cities as possible, away from artificial light sources and light pollution (Soydugan, 2020). The goal of this study is to analyze the astro-tourism potential of Isparta Province's Melik Plateau, which is located distant from the city center and has little light pollution. The study introduced the ideas of light pollution and astro-tourism for this aim, and a SWOT analysis of the Melik Plateau and astro-tourism operations was conducted. The study is expected to contribute to the literature and studies on destination planning.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Light pollution

Light pollution is pollution created by artificial outdoor lighting, as opposed to natural light sources like the sun and moon. Even though the sky and stars are brighter at night, light pollution created by artificial lighting makes it difficult to see the stars clearly. In this context, proper lighting practices in cities and rural regions are required to protect the sky from light pollution. Furthermore, air pollution is another factor that stops us from looking up at the sky. It is critical to create a conducive setting for studying the sky. The sky will not be seen clearly if there is cloud, fog, or pollution in the air. It will discourage tourists visiting the region for astro-tourism from looking up at the sky in this situation (Karaca et al., 2018: 2).

To battle light pollution and conserve dark areas, the International Dark-Sky Association (IDA) was founded in the state of Arizona in the United States in 1988. IDA engages in a variety of efforts with the goal of conserving and passing on the existing darkness of the sky to future generations. IDA achieves its objectives through trainings that promote ecologically sustainable outdoor lighting and raise societal awareness (IDA, 2022).

IDA was one of the first organizations in the world to work on the protection of black skies and the development of astronomy tourism about 20 years ago, fighting light pollution on a global scale. They created the International Dark Sky

Places (IDSPC) initiative in 2001 with the purpose of encouraging public institutions, parks, and protected areas to maintain and improve night sky quality through appropriate lighting rules and public education. The major goal of this initiative is to address light pollution while simultaneously creating visitor demand through a variety of programs that are run by astronomers as well as locals (Collison & Poe, 2013; C-Sánchez et al., 2019).

Tourists that are interested in astronomy want to visit observatories or important archaeoastronomy locations where they can watch the stars. But the natural black sky places of amazing beauty are even more essential. For night sky observation or any other sky phenomenon to be experienced or viewed, two main conditions must be met. There is no light pollution in the area, and the atmospheric conditions are ideal (C-Sánchez et al., 2019).

Light pollution affects more than 80% of the world's population due to artificial lighting. This means that almost a third of the population is unable to see the Milky Way (Falchi et al., 2016). Furthermore, 99% of Europe's and America's highly urbanized populations live beneath lightly polluted skies. As a result, Europe and North America are major markets for astronomy tourism, with public observatories, planetariums, and IDA approved sites ranking among the world's top destinations (Bjelajac et al., 2021: 27-28).

2.2. *Astro-tourism*

Astro-tourism is a sort of special interest tourism that relies on tourists' celestial activities such as sky-watching and astrophotography. It is a subgenre of nature-based tourism (Cater, 2010; Weaver, 2011). The physical qualities of the site, such as mountains, woods, rivers, and beaches, are used to diversify nature-based tourism (Kim & Brown, 2012). Astro-tourism, which is one of the specialized elements of nature-based tourism, is followed by travelers with expert knowledge and abilities who are interested in the visual face of the sky as well as the destination's distinctive qualities (Eagle, 2014). This sort of tourism is based on the physical characteristics of the location, combining the earth's features with the globally shared sky (Keller, 2010; Collison & Poe, 2013).

Rainbows, sunrise and sunset, solar and lunar eclipses, equinoxes, and planetary conjunctions are examples of astronomical and celestial events that can be observed through astronomy tourism (Ingle, 2010: 98). In terms of both encouraging astro tours in natural regions and contributing to the development of rural astro-tourist locations, growing interest in astronomy and the sky is an important tourism activity. In astro-tourism destinations, finding and using telescopes for sky observations is the most typical part. Astro-tourism activities are generally witnessed by a group of local or international tourists at night in rural regions across the world (Jacobs et al., 2020).

Astronomy events are unusual and unique nature activities that lead travelers to the center of the astronomical event, which are announced to the international audience. Many travelers around the world are interested in astronomical sights

(rainbows, sunsets, sunrises, etc.) and astronomical occurrences (solar and lunar eclipses, etc.) (Soleimani Najafabadi, 2012: 129). Stargazing walks, dark sky festivals, star parties, night horse rides, astro-photography, eclipse observations, meteor showers, and star recognition training are just a few of the astronomy-based recreational activities that make the region a popular tourist destination (Wassenaar, 2020: 132).

Astro-tourism can take the form of a variety of tourist activities in diverse locations. People can observe the stars with telescopes at the Night Station observatories in France and the United States (Weaver, 2011). Every year, a considerable number of “Aurora tourists” flock to Canada, Finland, Iceland, Greenland, Scotland, and Russia to see the visible northern lights (Soleimani et al., 2019). “Astronomical ecotourism camps” are organized in the deserts of Jordan and Chile to observe the night sky or solar occurrences, as well as participate in other ecotourism activities. The Great Lakes region of North America features a specialized tourist product known as “Long Ship Astronomy Ships”, which provides tourists with a once-in-a-lifetime opportunity to observe the sky from the sea. Furthermore, national parks in the United States provide a variety of interesting and diverse experiences.

Astro-tourism activities can be carried out as various touristic activities in different destinations. At the Night Station observatories in France and the USA, people can watch the stars using telescopes (Weaver, 2011). Canada, Finland, Iceland, Greenland, Scotland and Russia attract large numbers of Aurora tourists each year for the northern lights visible to the naked eye (Soleimani et al., 2019). In Jordan and Chile, astronomical ecotourism camps are held in the deserts to observe the night sky or solar events and other ecotourism activities. In North America, the Great Lakes region has a niche tourist product called the Long Ship Astronomy Ships, which offers tourists a unique opportunity to experience sky observations from the sea. Furthermore, national parks in the United States provide visitors with a variety of unique astronomy products (Collison & Poe, 2013).

2.3. Melik Plateau

The International Association of Dark Sky Parks has developed 130 dark sky parks throughout the world. It is found in Scotland, Finland, Austria, Canada, Germany, Croatia, New Zealand, South Korea, Japan, and Hungary, though it is most common in the United States. In Turkey, there is currently no official or designated dark park. Scientists have given the Melik Plateau National Park in Isparta Province the moniker of “Turkey’s Darkest Spot” based on their findings. The value of the Melik plateau Kadir scale was found to be 22.04. This rating indicates that Melik Plateau is a dark park candidate for Golden Class Dark Park classification. According to the Bortle Dark Sky Scale (IDA) measurement categorization, the plateau is in the Bortle-2 Dark Sky class (Yalçın & Karabacak, 2022: 31).

The Kızıldağ National Park contains the Melik Plateau. Pine forests and Dedegöl Mountain views can be found on the Melik plateau. On the plateau,

mountain climbing and sky observation activities take place on Dedegöl Mountain. During the summer months, the Milky Way galaxy can be viewed with the naked eye from the Melik plateau, one of Turkey's darkest regions. Every year at Antalya Saklıkent and Isparta Melik Plateau, these events, which are evaluated as astro-tourism activities, are held (Karabacak, 2021).

It is one of the best sites in the Melik Plateau for mountain hiking, camping, and climbing. Mountaineers from all across Turkey pitch tents on the Melik Plateau, which is located above the Pnargözü Cave, and every year during the Mountaineering Festival, they climb Dedegöl Mountain. The summit of Dedegöl Mountain is climbed during the three-day Mountaineering Festival. In terms of indigenous vegetation, the Melik Plateau and Dedegöl Mountain surrounds are extremely diverse. Mountaineers are drawn to Karagöl, which grows exclusively on the outskirts of Dedegöl mountain, and Dedegül flower, which grows only on the outskirts of Dedegöl Mountain.

3. Methodology

In the research, it is aimed to determine the astro-tourism potential of Melik Plateau in Isparta Province, which is far from the city center and has low light pollution. For this purpose, qualitative research method was used in the research, which gives the opportunity to obtain in-depth information (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). In qualitative research, observation, interview, document, and speech analysis are often utilized data collection techniques. Document/text analysis is the process of thoroughly scanning written materials holding information linked to the facts or events investigated in the research and constructing a new integrity from this data (Creswell, 2002).

The SWOT analysis technique can be used to assess the strengths and weaknesses of an organization, sector, investment, country, or geographical region based on its features, as well as the opportunities and dangers posed by environmental factors that are controllable or not (Karadeniz et al., 2007: 196). Internal review of the company identifies strengths and shortcomings; external evaluation identifies opportunities and dangers. External evaluation entails assessing political, economic, social, technological, and competitive factors in order to discover opportunities and dangers, whereas internal evaluation examines the entire company to determine its strengths and shortcomings (Dyson, 2004: 632).

4. Results and Discussion

The goal of this study is to assess the region's astro-tourism potential on the Melik Plateau in Isparta Province using a SWOT analysis along with document and text analysis. The region's strengths and limitations, as well as the potential and risks to the region's astro-tourism, were all attempted to be established through this investigation. Table 1 below contains the SWOT analysis data for the area of Melik Plateau astro-tourism activities.

Table 1. SWOT analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ It is one of Turkey's darkest spots; ▪ It is an area suitable for astro-tourism; ▪ Unspoilt natural environment; ▪ Scenic viewpoints, open and green spaces; ▪ Ability to do mountain climbing activity; ▪ Being a rich area in terms of cultural and natural assets; ▪ Carrying out national and international promotional activities on astro-tourism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of investment in tourism infrastructure in the region; ▪ Poor transportation infrastructure to the plateau; ▪ Obstacles brought by the protection status; ▪ The absence of an observatory in the area; ▪ Insufficient promotion and advertising activities for the time being; ▪ Insufficient infrastructure to meet the needs.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The area is in a better position than Europe in terms of light pollution; ▪ The richness of forest resources; ▪ Undisturbed natural areas; ▪ Carrying out studies on astro-tourism and astro photography in the destination; ▪ Conducting awareness studies on astro-tourism; ▪ The high tourism potential; ▪ State measures and investment allocations for the protection of natural and cultural assets; ▪ Regional Development Agency's support of astro-tourism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The risk of fire and pollution arising from daily tour activities in the area; ▪ Poor communication between stakeholders; ▪ The indifference of private sector entrepreneurs to invest; ▪ Nature damage that may occur during the investment phase.

Source: Author's elaboration

5. Conclusion

With each passing day, global travel and recreation trends take on a whole new dimension. Observing the sky and being curious about the universe continue to pique attention as tourism and leisure activities today, as they have done throughout history. The goal of this study is to use a SWOT analysis to look at the astro-tourism activities on the Melik Plateau. Melk Plateau, in the province of Isparta, is a suitable location for astro-tourism. As a result, it is a region on the plateau that can appeal to special interest groups such as sky watching, astro-photography, and so on. The expenditures in infrastructure and superstructure required to realize astro-tourist activities in the area, as well as the opening of the plateau to tourism, will aid regional growth.

The strengths of Melik Plateau in terms of astro-tourism, according to the results of the SWOT analysis conducted as part of the research, are that it is one of Turkey's darkest spots, that it is an area suitable for astro-tourism, that it has an unspoiled environment, cultural and natural assets, and that it can be used for a variety of tourism activities. The lack of tourism investments in the region, the poor transportation facilities, the hurdles posed by the protected status, the infrastructure's inability to satisfy needs, the observatory, and the lack of opportunities are all weaknesses. The area has low light pollution due to its dark spot, natural beauty and abundant forest resources, state-protected natural and

cultural assets, it is a place that can be invested in, and its tourism potential is strong. Fire dangers and pollution from the region's regular visitation, as well as a lack of communication among stakeholders, are all threats.

According to studies conducted in the area, the Plateau is a contender for designation as a "International Dark Sky Park". Several proposals are in the works to transform the region into a Dark Sky Park with little bungalow-style dwellings where anyone can observe. In addition, required studies for the Melik Plateau's membership in the International Darksky Association (IDA) and other internationally recognized international networks should be conducted in order to boost the Melik Plateau's international recognition.

Suggestions:

- The regions where astro-tourism and observation activities will be carried out in the area, as well as the establishment of observatories, must be determined.
- Institutions with jurisdiction should take steps to limit light pollution in the area.
- Activities linked to astrotourism in the vicinity should be investigated, as well as any relevant planning studies.
- In terms of astro-tourism, the location should be promoted both nationally and internationally.
- Studies of settlement areas should be conducted in accordance with the astro-tourism topic.
- It is vital to strike a balance between protection and utilization in future developments in the area.

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